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Introduction

In this brief essay, I recount a number of anecdotes which have bearing on how emotions enter the design of technologies. My intentions are not merely self-indulgent, but to use these stories as clues or data in trying to make sense of how we might more explicitly recognise emotion in design. I discuss my conclusions in the last section.

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Emotion is a subset of the irrational in design. In the anecdotal evidence I describe here, humour, play, aesthetics, and their cultural connotations are as important as emotion. What is at stake here is the *irrational* in design, those aspects that do not directly concern an artifact's utility or purpose, but which still strongly influence how it is experienced and used. While it is probably possible to disentangle emotion from these other aspects of irrationality, these aspects are closely related. In what follows I will use the term "emotion" as a shorthand for irrationality in general.

Clues

Many years ago, I had the opportunity to visit Skywalker Ranch, Lucas Film's sprawling complex north of San Francisco. I was there to meet with an academy award winning sound designer to talk about the work I was doing then in auditory interfaces. He allowed me to show him a few videos—an auditory version of the Mac Finder, a collaborative interface that used sound, and so on. When they were done, I waited for his comments. Finally, he spoke:

"It seems that you've designed the sounds for a humorous effect," he said.

This shocked me. It simply didn't make sense. The interfaces were based on a fairly elaborate theory about how people obtain information from sound, and the sorts of functions that sound might perform. This was solid research work—and he was commenting on the emotional overtones of the sounds? It bothered me, but soon after returning to my normal working environment, I shrugged off his remark.

When I moved to England, my wife—then my girlfriend—stayed in California for a few years. We wrote each other email constantly. But after a while, it degenerated into a ritual exchange of messages

about what we'd done that day. And after a few months, we had almost completely stopped using email to keep in touch. Instead, we used the phone, or even postcards and letters.

While I was working at Rank Xerox EuroPARC, we had a mediaspace setup that allowed us to network live video around the building, so that we could use it to communicate with one another, attend meetings, etc.

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Occasionally we would play with the technology we had around. For instance, we put a small camera into the head of a mannequin and set it up in our commons area. The idea was that people would notice the human form faster than they would a camera—we'd had problems with people not realising the commons area was part of the media space, as for instance when one of the security guards changed his trousers without realising he might be seen. And it worked, too: people noticed the mannequin very quickly when they entered the room. The problem was that it often seemed eerie and disturbing to them.

On another occasion, we set up an audio processor so that when I talked to my boss, my voice was high-pitched and his was low and rumbling. It was amusing, how it amplified the power relationships, and even more so when we switched it.

It was great fun pursuing these technological diversions. Of course we never took them seriously, they were just play.

Still during my time at EuroPARC, I visited the Royal College of Art to help direct a student project about sound in the interface. The task was to design an agent that would scan the net searching for information you wanted, playing sounds to indicate its progress. The students' work was very strange to me. For instance, one designed a little submarine that would float around the bottom of your screen, then disappear into a little tube when you sent it to scan the net. As it searched, it made pinging sonar noises, and when it found something, it would fire it back with a flushing sound. Ridiculous—yet delightful. Work like that stuck in my mind and made me happy about technology. A little later, I joined the RCA.

Recognition One of my first projects at the RCA, sponsored by Apple Computer, involved designing a schedule for the course to be projected in a public space. The idea was that the affordances of such a display would lead to greater accountability amongst the staff and students of the course. We displayed a very simple version over a few months, and it worked. Meetings tended to start on time, and not get rescheduled too often.

But the visualisation seemed ugly, so we set a student project to come up with different representations of the schedule. We got about 6 projects back. What became clear was that the differences had less to do with the functionality of the visualisations—though of course these varied—and more to do with the cultural implications of the aesthetics they employed. Some seemed friendly and happy, with smi-

ling people or flowers representing events. Others seemed cold or even hostile, using abstract slabs of material or even gigantic cogwheels that emphasised the mechanical nature of the school year. It dawned on me that perhaps the most interesting research questions concerned the emotional connotations of the designs.

One of our students, Rob Strong, did a project in which he addressed communication among separated lovers (Strong & Gaver, 1996). He proposed three devices. My favorite was "The Feather." According to his scenario, the travelling partner would bring along a small picture frame, showing the couple or the loved one, to be displayed in his or her hotel room. Picking up the frame for a closer look would send a signal via telephone or internet to the couple's home. This would activate the Feather object, a furniture-sized object consisting of a wooden box

on long legs, with a clear plexiglass cone projecting upwards. A fan would turn on in the box, causing a small white feather to drift around inside the cone. The effect on the local partner would be similar to seeing his or her lover smile across a crowded room.

This struck me as a project that should be of interest to researchers studying technology mediated communication. We presented it at a conference on Computer Supported Collaborative Design, though I'm not sure it made any real effect on the community.

Recently Tony Dunne and I took part in the EU sponsored Presence Project, in which we worked with seven partners from four countries to develop new technologies to increase the presence of the elderly in their local communities (Gaver & Dunne, 1999). Our designs focused on the Bijlmer, a planned community south of Amsterdam with a dangerous

reputation. In our contacts with the local elders, we found that while security concerns were real, they also were proud of living in a culturally rich community and wanted to express that within the Netherlands.

Our designs focused around allowing a growing wave of community expression to emerge. People in their flats were periodically asked to choose their favorite image from a set of about a hundred gathered from the elders.

Their choices were used to control sloganbenches, which showed short statements written by the elders about their attitudes or beliefs. In addition, passersby could also select from among the slogans contained by the benches to reflect their own interests or concerns. The slogans showing at a given time, in turn, were used to control images shown on an imagebank—an elongated cabinet containing five 28-inch monitors—meant to give glimpses into the Bijlmer to people travelling on its outskirts.

The benches and imagebank worked well, eliciting a great deal of interest from people living in the Bijlmer. Children were especially drawn to the devices, curious about the slightly strange designs and further intrigued by the slogans themselves. It wasn't that the designs themselves were emotional, or elicited strong emotions beyond curiosity. Instead, they served well to create a space in which emotions could occur, but not be directed, a space in which communications created by the elders elicited intrigue and curiosity in viewers.

Lessons

Reflecting on these experiences, I come to several conclusions:

There is no such thing as a neutral interface. Any design will elicit emotions from users, or convey emotions from its designer, whether or not the designer intends this or is even conscious of it. Interfaces can be designed for neutrality, but the effect is not neutral in the sense that it allows emotions to be neglected; instead it is a choice with its own implications. Ignoring the emotional connotations of design can have unpredictable effects.

Possible roles of emotion in design need to be differentiated. If the irrational is inescapable, it can be controlled, to a great degree, through design. The issue becomes what role emotions should play in artifacts. It is possible, for instance, that designs should:

- *Elicit* emotions on the part of users. This is unavoidable, as I discuss above, but can be shaped to various ends. For instance, Dunne's *value fictions* (Dunne, 1999) are technologically plausible but socially implausible artifacts; the unsettling emotions they evoke in viewers motivate a questioning of the cultural values that make the designs implausible.

- *Allow* for emotions. People inevitably appropriate designs into their everyday emotional lives. Designs can allow for this in more or less sensitive and flexible ways, however, by providing resources that can be appropriated to emotional ends. This might include the number and kinds of type-faces available in a word-processing package or the degree to which drawing packages allow fluid curves or sketchy effects as well as rectilinear lines. But we can go much further, as has been done in attempts to support emotional communication.
- *Communicate emotions* between people. Designs such as the Feather (and other work developed at the RCA, MIT, Stanford, and elsewhere) suggest that technology may support emotional communication more directly than traditional media. Often such designs rely on the artifacts' eliciting the emotions that are meant to be conveyed—the drifting feather is poetic and evocative even when it does not signal the attention of a distant lover, for instance. Another tactic might be to constrain the medium to encourage intimacy—for instance, the Intimate View camera, a concept design developed by Heather Martin and myself, suggests that devices specialised to capture and transmit magnified images might allow lovers to share moments of intense focus, whether mundane or erotic.
- *Recognise* emotions explicitly. Using physiological sensors or behavioural cues, digital products might be able to surmise their users' emotional states and react accordingly. For instance, upon sensing frustration software might automatically open a help package, or to-do lists might automatically suggest tasks depending on their users' mood.
 - *Have* emotions themselves. In recognising and reacting to their users' emotions, we might be tempted to attribute emotional intelligence to digital devices. If an automated to-do list also took into account task urgency, dogmatically insisting on tasks despite its user's displeasure, we might even be tempted to attribute it with its own emotions. This could be designed for explicitly, ending in software that could be happy when users succeed or sad when they fail. Devices might share their owners' emotions, or even have conflicting ones.

Designing systems that elicit, allow for, communicate, recognise, or share emotions all appears achievable (and sometimes inevitable).

The question becomes what is desirable. In considering this, I reach a last conclusion:

Designs that make emotions explicit are potentially dangerous. Artifacts that recognise or share our emotions are likely to rely on explicit representations of emotional states—ours and theirs. This is problematic for two reasons.

First, devices which rely on knowing our emotions are likely to be wrong, not only because of the fallibility of their sensory and inference systems, not only because emotions are likely to be rich, multidimensional, fluid, and difficult to represent, but because reading the emotions of others is inherently a difficult task, prone to misunderstandings and mistakes. **53**

Second, making explicit what is normally inexplicit has large repercussions. Imagine, for instance, being unaware that you are apprehensive about meeting with your boss until your to-do list points it out. Worse, imagine your boss is looking over your shoulder. The problem is that a large amount of contextual information would be necessary to develop interfaces which show the tact and sensitivity of even the clumsiest human. In the end, recognising and even having emotions is insufficient for emotional intelligence.

References

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